

Perioperative Opioid Reduction in Orthopedic Spine Surgeries

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Background

- The opioid epidemic is a public health crisis that encompasses several public health areas, calling for federal and state involvement to reduce opioid use and overdoses
- Orthopedic surgeons are one of the top opioid prescribers in the U.S.
- No standardized approach of multimodal analgesia in spine surgeries
 - No Enhanced Recovery After Surgery protocol

Significance:

- Perioperative opioids use in surgeries
- Use of multimodal analgesia & ERAS initiatives in surgical populations
- No current standard of optimization for spinal surgical patients

Problem Statement

- Perioperative opioids use in surgeries
- Multimodal analgesia & ERAS initiatives use among many surgical populations
- No current standard of optimization or multimodal approach used for spinal surgical patients
- Perioperative implementation of a clinical guide during spinal surgeries → reduce the consumption of opioids

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project is two-fold:

- To conduct a comprehensive review of literature of current practices to identify effective strategies in decreasing opioid use perioperatively for spinal procedures
- To develop a clinical checklist, based on current literature, for reducing perioperative opioid use.

Literature Review

Key Findings:

- Success of checklists in the clinical setting
- Multimodal perioperative approach for managing post-operative pain limits opioid administration
- No standard clinical checklist for perioperative opioid reduction in orthopedic spine surgeries

Medications	Dose	Disadvantages	Advantages
Gabapentin	100-1200 mg	Sedation and dizziness	Reduces neuropathic pain
NSAIDS (Ketorolac)	15-30 mg	Bleeding, delays bone healing, excreted via kidneys (careful in elderly), analgesic ceiling	Analgesic adjunct, no sedation or respiratory depressive effects, anti-inflammatory
Acetaminophen	325-1000 mg q4-6 hrs	Analgesic ceiling, risk for liver damage if used >24 hours	Analgesic and antipyretic effects, inexpensive and safe
Dexmedetomidine	0.2- 0.5 mcg/kg/hr	Decreased HR and BP	No respiratory depression
Ketamine	0.5 mg/kg bolus	Emergence delirium Side effects: increases HR, increased salivation, GI symptoms	Significant side effects only in large doses
Dexamethasone	4-8 mg	increases blood sugar and increases risk of infection	Anti-emetic and anti-inflammatory effects
Magnesium	20-50 mg/kg bolus	Contraindicated in parturient	Reduces opioid consumption for 24 hours

Conceptual Framework – Iowa Model

Clinical Checklist

Plan for Implementation and Evaluation

- Settings:** Kaiser Permanente Facility with high volume of orthopedic spine surgeries
- Participants:** Anesthesia providers
- Evaluation of checklist efficacy
 - Survey at 3 and 6 months

Discussion

Limitations:

- Absence of controlled substances
- Time constraints
- Current KP protocols already in place

Future Limitations:

- Noncompliance by medical staff
- Inability of checklist to be incorporated into EMR
- Staff unfamiliarity with medications
- Routine mentality in staff

Recommendations:

- Implement at Kaiser Permanente Facility with high volume of orthopedic spine surgeries
- Potential for reduction in perioperative opioid consumption
- Useful tool for anesthesia providers to incorporate multimodal analgesia